

Hormonal modulation of plant growth: the role of auxin perception

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The organisation of growth and development in vascular plants appears to be highly adapted to meet the specific demands of a sessile, autotrophic habit. Many of the characteristic features of plant development are associated with the activities of five groups of phytohormones. Each of the phytohormones has the ability to influence fundamentally a remarkable variety of developmental and physiological processes. This ability has been widely documented but remains to be explained. Here we describe how recent breakthroughs in the analysis and understanding of eucaryotic signal transduction are being applied, in conjunction with technical advances in molecular genetics, to elucidate the molecular basis of the phytohormonal properties of auxin. Both auxin concentration, and the sensitivity of plant cells to this phytohormone have been implicated as important parameters in auxin action. We describe recent molecular biological approaches to assess the contribution made by each of these parameters. Emphasis is given to a description of recent genetic and biochemical progress towards identification of the molecular targets of the auxin signal and the molecular components involved in its subsequent transduction.

Introduction

Vascular plants are multicellular eucaryotes with extraordinary developmental characteristics that can be viewed as highly specialised adaptations to their sessile, autotrophic habit. It is known that in many instances plant development can be dramatically influenced by a set of five structurally simple phytohormones, each of which can elicit a remarkable variety of responses (Fig. 1). Despite their demonstrable ability to modify cellular differentiation, the contribution of phytohormones to ontogeny and the mechanisms of their action remain to be determined (Davies, 1987). Experimental and theoretical approaches to this problem have prompted a longstanding debate concerning the relative importance of variations in phytohormone concentration versus differential sensitivity of different plant cells to particular phytohormones (Trewavas and Cleland, 1983; Weyers, 1984; Cannay, 1985). The objectives of this review are,

firstly, to summarize current understanding and interpretations of the characteristic features of vascular plant development and phytohormone action, with emphasis on the auxins; secondly, to discuss the importance of cell sensitivity and auxin perception in development, along with recent experimental approaches that address this problem; and finally, to describe initial progress in identification of the molecular targets of the auxin signal at the responding cell as well as the molecules responsible for the subsequent intracellular transduction of the signal. However, if we are to understand the role of phytohormones in vascular plant development, we must consider the specific developmental characteristics of vascular plants and the biological demands that they meet.

A consequence of the sessile habit and phototrophism of vascular plants is that their survival frequently depends upon their capacity to tolerate predation and local environmental fluctuation, as well as their ability to exploit limited local resources in competition with neighbouring plants (Trewavas, 1986). These requirements are reflected in the body plan of vascular plants which is characteristically organised in a simple

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The Classical Phytohormones

Plant hormone	Structure	Typical Concentration in tissues	Synthesis	Transport	SELECTED DEVELOPMENTAL RESPONSES				
					Growth rate	Rooting	Fruit development	Juvenile-adult phase change	Dormancy
Auxin	 Indole-3-acetic acid	100 pmole·g ⁻¹	meristem leaf primordia developing seeds	cell to cell phloem	*	*	*	*	
Ethylene		40 pmole·g ⁻¹ ·hr ⁻¹	most tissues	diffusion	*	*	*		*
Cytokinin	 Zeatin	100-1000 pmole·g ⁻¹	root tips developing seeds	xylem	*	*	*		*
Abscisic acid	 GA1	80-4000 pmole·g ⁻¹	mature leaves	phloem	*			*	*
Gibberellin	 GA1	0.3 pmole·g ⁻¹	young shoot tissue developing seeds	phloem xylem	*	*	*	*	*

Fig. 1. Summary of biological properties of plant growth regulators. Asterisks indicate some of the processes that have been reported to be stimulated or inhibited by particular phytohormones in at least one experimental system.

reiterative fashion, often with branching. For example, angiosperms consist of repetitions of a module structure comprising the bud plus subtended leaf above ground, and below ground, repetitions of root meristems. Individual plant cells retain a remarkable and widely documented regenerative capacity, with many cells remaining totipotent, even after completing an initial programme of developmental differentiation. Indeed specialisation appears to have been minimized and individual plant cells within a tissue are often considered relatively isolated and independent. These features are of specific advantage to sessile organisms as they allow predation and environmental damage to be tolerated owing to the functional redundancy of the repeated modules, whilst allowing lost tissues to be replaced by regeneration of damaged tissue and by continued growth of the undamaged units (Trewavas, 1986). In contrast, organisms based on highly specialised, functionally integrated body plans risk the loss of essential functions from even limited damage. In addition, branching of shoot and root systems allows efficient exploitation of the available environmental resources.

To facilitate the reiterative growth pattern, and in stark contrast to the mammalian embryo, only a rudimentary body plan is laid down in the plant embryo. It consists of the primary axis and the centers of cell division, the meristems. It is from the meristems that, after seed germination, an indefinite number of adult organs continue to arise until the onset of senescence.

Plants possess numerous sensory perception mechanisms to detect a variety of environmental signals, including light and gravity. It is important to note here that in many instances the response of plants to such environmental signals is not behavioural, but develop-

mental. Meristematic cells differentiate continuously into new tissues and organs throughout ontogeny, and certain characters of the new structures (for example the shape and thickness of leaves) or of established structures (for example the rate of stem elongation), are modified to best exploit the fluctuating biotic and abiotic environment. This environmentally induced plasticity affects many aspects of plant development and appears to be well adapted to the sessile photoautotrophic habit. Interestingly, in many instances it is these plastic developmental responses that are found to be particularly sensitive to the action of the five phytohormones (Trewavas, 1986). In fact, since the early observations of Darwin on tropic growth responses, phytohormones have been promoted as regulators of plant growth although their precise role is still debated. As the preceding paragraphs have illustrated, plant development differs considerably from that of animals, and is further distinguished by the lack of movement of individual cells within the plant body during ontogeny, hence elucidation of the mechanisms of phytohormone action may lead us to novel principles in developmental adaptation (Goldberg, 1988).

Botanists have questioned, over many years, the applicability of the animal hormonal analogy to an understanding of the activity of the phytohormones. This longstanding debate has been concerned with (1) the different chemical structures of the known plant and animal hormones, (2) the importance of transport of phytohormones to the responding tissue from a distant site of synthesis, (3) the remarkable diversity of responses elicited by each of the phytohormones versus the relative specificity of animal hormones and (4) sensitivity characteristics of some physiological re-

sponses evoked by phytohormones (for discussion see Firn, 1986; Guern, 1987). It is important to note that plants, in contrast to animals, lack specific endocrine organs for spatially localised hormone production. This difference in organisation is not surprising as plants show relatively little anatomical specialisation. As a consequence of such differences in anatomical organisation and of the apparently rather autonomous status of individual plant cells in a tissue, we may reasonably expect different principles to apply to organisation of the production, movement and sequestration of phytohormones.

Despite the interesting developmental features of higher plants, we have a paltry knowledge of the processes involved in perception of the phytohormonal signal and elicitation of the response. Some elements of signal perception and response pathways appear to be common to all eukaryotic phyla (Palme et al., 1989; 1990a,c; Ma et al., 1990; Nitschke et al., 1990); however, the challenge will be to unravel the basis of the specific differences responsible for the perplexing adaptive potential of plant developmental processes. As the first step in the response to a phytohormonal signal must be its perception, the experimental analysis of this process will be the subject of most of what follows.

Our present interest in understanding the molecular details of plant hormone action is kindled not only by the exciting scientific prospects, but also by the hope that scientific progress will contribute to improvements in many aspects of the breeding and cultivation of crop plants.

Plant hormones influence development of higher plants at multiple levels

Most of the known biological effects of phytohormones have been elucidated by exogenous application of these hormones to plants, explants or tissues in culture. For example wounded or excised tissue can be induced to proliferate as undifferentiated callus by application of a combination of auxin and cytokinin; by increasing the auxin to cytokinin ratio the tissue can be induced to initiate root production, and by increasing the cytokinin component to initiate shoot production (Murashige and Skoog, 1962). However, questions remained over the interpretation of the results gained by these techniques and their relevance for phytohormone action in vivo. The advent of genetic engineering of plants then made it possible to change phytohormone concentrations in whole plants and from within. The tools for the genetic engineering of plants were presented by the plant pathogenic soil bacterium *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*. Infection of susceptible plants by *A. tumefaciens* leads to cell proliferation, resulting in the formation of localized tumours (crown galls; Fig. 2A).

The molecular basis for this cell proliferation is the integration of a part of the bacterial Ti-plasmid into the plant genome. The analysis of this transferred DNA, the T-DNA, has demonstrated the presence of both auxin- (*IaaM* and *IaaH*) and cytokinin-biosynthetic (*IptZ*) genes. The simultaneous expression of these genes leads to higher concentrations of auxin and cytokinin and hence to undifferentiated tumours (for review see Zambryski et al., 1989). However, expression of only the auxin biosynthetic genes leads to a reorganisation of the tumours, resulting in the initiation of roots from the tumours. Conversely, a stimulation of shoot production was observed upon increased internal production of only cytokinin by the T-DNA encoded *IptZ* gene (Buchmann et al., 1985; Smigocki and Owens, 1988). In this way elevated levels of auxin or cytokinin could be linked to initiation of morphogenetic responses, i.e., abnormal stimulation of root- or shoot proliferation, respectively.

Klee et al. (1987) engineered the *A. tumefaciens* encoded genes for auxin biosynthesis to allow their constitutive or tissue-specific expression in plants and attempted to specifically correlate the phenotypic consequences with changes in internal auxin levels. Transgenic petunia plants expressing the *A. tumefaciens IaaM* gene resulted in approximately a 10-fold increase of endogenous IAA levels. All plants showed morphological abnormalities including an increase in the size of epidermal and palisade cells, an increase in the size of intercellular space resulting in thickened leaves, and a small elongation of the stems coupled with an increase in xylem and phloem content. The effects of the raised IAA concentration were, however, largely quantitative and neither affected reproductive capacity, induced new morphogenetic events, nor prevented growth. The differential responsiveness of various cells and tissues within the plant suggest that the nature of the response in each case is a function of the responding system rather than of the evoking substance. The different magnitude of the response elicited by auxin in different tissues could be explained by either differential sensitivity of each tissue to auxin, or differential distribution of auxin within the tissue. This long-standing conflict, that has attracted much theoretical debate, will be resolved only after the introduction of techniques to adequately measure phytohormone concentration and cell sensitivity in situ. This approach confirms previous observations, and increasingly sophisticated genetic engineering will allow a more detailed analysis of the effect of localised alteration of hormone production on specific tissues (Finnegan et al., 1989; Spena et al., 1989; Spena, 1990).

It is equally conceivable that an alteration of plant growth characteristics is not induced only by changed phytohormone concentration, but also by modification of the perception of the phytohormonal signal and the

Fig. 2. Tumors induced on a tobacco plant by *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* (A) and *Agrobacterium rhizogenes* (B).

transduction pathways downstream. Indeed, genes encoded by *Agrobacterium rhizogenes* T-DNA affect not only auxin biosynthesis, but dramatically raise the sensitivity to extracellularly applied auxins by apparently influencing the auxin signal transduction pathway (Shen et al., 1988), resulting in the well known hairy-root syndrome (Ackermann et al., 1977; Fig. 2B). Although the genes responsible for the induction of neoplastic root growth as well as other growth abnormalities associated with this disease were demonstrated by gene-transfer experiments to be encoded by a segment of *A. rhizogenes* T-DNA, the T_L -DNA, the biochemical and physiological basis of function of these genes is still far from being understood (Spena et al., 1987; Schmülling et al., 1988). Nevertheless, elucidation of the strategies used by various *Agrobacteria* to evoke morphogenetic responses either by raising phytohormone levels or by changing sensitivity to phytohormones encourages us to search for the molecular targets of auxin action and their coupled signalling pathways.

Mutants aid in the search for targets of plant hormone action

One of the reasons for the present poor knowledge of plant signalling units has been the difficulty in devising efficient schemes for genetic selection of plant receptor mutants. This is primarily because it has not been possible to predict the specific phenotypes of particular receptor mutants. Precise design and expression of dominant loss-of-function mutants in *in vitro* animal cell cultures or in transgenic animals can interfere with crucial signalling steps and thus cause severe developmental defects (for example Tan et al., 1990). By analogy, we would predict pleiotropic growth alterations for mutations interfering with central perception steps in plant hormone signalling. In the absence of precise knowledge of auxin-receptor-deficient phenotypes, selection for dramatic growth alterations will represent the major morphological criterion for isolation of putative auxin-receptor mutants, although any changes in central hormone metabolism may result in related phe-

notypes as well. Hence, on the basis of current knowledge, selection for increased resistance to growth-inhibiting concentrations of auxins, or alternatively, for growth at normally insufficient concentrations, provide the most common selection criteria. Such work has been performed largely with *Arabidopsis thaliana*, owing to its small size, its short generation time, and simple genomic organization which make this plant very attractive for diverse genetic screenings (for review see Meyerowitz, 1987; King, 1988). Using resistance to toxic concentrations of various plant hormones, several mutants resistant to abscisic acid, ethylene, and auxin analogs such as naphthylacetic acid (NAA) or 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) were isolated (Mirza et al., 1984; Koorneef et al., 1984; Estelle and Somerville, 1987; Bleeker et al., 1988; Wilson et al., 1990). Mutants resistant to toxic concentrations of auxins were shown to display pleiotropic morphological changes in roots, leaves, and flowers (Estelle and Somerville, 1987). In particular the *axr2* mutation located on chromosome 3 conferred resistance not only to auxin but also to other growth regulators such as abscisic acid and ethylene (Wilson et al., 1990). Although these may be hormone receptor mutants, it is equally conceivable that the mutation affects hormone transport systems or other elements of the response pathway. This is well illustrated by a tryptophan-requiring mutant from *A. thaliana* defective in anthranilate phosphoribosyltransferase, which accumulates anthranilic acid derivatives interfering with indole-3-acetic acid biosynthesis (Last and Fink, 1988). Surprisingly, the observed morphological defects, including slow growth, small crinkled leaves, and reduced apical dominance, resulting in a bushy appearance, are similar to those of the auxin-resistant locus (*axr1*; Estelle and Somerville, 1987). Additionally, the search for auxin auxotrophs has resulted in the identification of temperature-sensitive mutants of *Hyoscyamus muticus* and *Nicotiana plumbagenifolia* which, apparently defective in indole-3-acetic acid metabolism, have conditional lethal phenotypes (Oetiker et al., 1989). Nevertheless, there is little doubt that the isolation of these mutant loci by chromosome walking and their subsequent molecular characterization will significantly contribute to our understanding of plant hormone perception. Genetically defined alterations in hormone sensitivity provide an excellent bioassay for the functional relevance of hormone binding proteins representing putative receptors and help to reveal the various steps in the cascade of reactions initiated by plant hormones such as auxins.

Rapid induction of fast cellular responses by auxin

The developmental responses to auxin that have concerned us so far become apparent over a period of hours

or days. However, underlying these processes are some responses that can be perceived a few minutes after auxin application. Auxin-induced elongation growth in a variety of plants has been most thoroughly studied due to its short latency period of 10 to 15 min. Of special interest is the influence of auxin on the orientation of cortical microtubules at the outer wall of the outer epidermis of growing maize coleoptiles during tropic curvature (Bergfeld et al., 1988). This cell wall controls the elongation of the coleoptile, and curvature arises from different rates of cell elongation at both opposite flanks of the coleoptile. It has been demonstrated that 15 min after application of indole-3-acetic acid, reorientation of both microtubules and microfibrils from a longitudinal to a transverse direction is initiated and completed within 60 min. Most interestingly, the hormone was shown to act particularly at the growth-controlling wall of the coleoptile, thus allowing correlation of growth responses elicited by tropic stimuli with differential orientation of the microfilaments at each flank of the organ (Nick et al., 1990). Apart from changes in the filament system, auxin effects have been observed on the synthesis of cell wall matrix and polysaccharides (Brummell and Hall, 1985). Furthermore, changes in the electrical gradient of plant plasma membranes have been noted, which are among the most rapid alterations observed for plants. In coleoptiles, for example, auxin application induces a depolarization followed by a hyperpolarization assumed to result from stimulation of a plasmalemma associated H⁺-pumping ATPase (Cleland et al., 1977; Bates and Goldsmith, 1983; Libbenga et al., 1986). Similar effects on the transmembrane potential have been observed in a large variety of plant tissues. This response may represent one of the long-sought physiological reactions to auxin, and has led to the use of such electrophysiological effects as functional tests for this hormone (Ephritikine et al., 1987; Barbier-Brygoo et al., 1989). A more detailed analysis of the proteins involved may allow future use of this technique as a means to dissect the primary auxin-responsive elements. Although the molecular targets have not yet been identified, it is conceivable that alterations of electrical potential may represent one of the early signals that leads to the activation of long-term responses such as initiation of cell division or differentiation processes.

From a series of recent studies it is evident that auxins can specifically and rapidly alter the abundance of several mRNA species (for review see Hagen, 1989). Of particular interest has been a group of RNAs identified from soybean (McClure and Guilfoyle, 1987, 1989). The increase in abundance of these small auxin up RNAs (SAUR) apparently precedes cell elongation. They are induced after 2.5 min by application of 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) and accumulate up to 50-fold over untreated controls. Of specific interest is a

recently identified mRNA from tobacco mesophyll cells which is abundantly expressed in response to auxins before onset of cell division (Takahashi et al., 1989). Detailed analysis of promoter activity of the corresponding gene as well as others isolated in the recent years will help to isolate key elements that control auxin-specific gene regulation (Koncz and Schell, 1986; Van der Zaal et al., 1987; Ainley et al., 1988; McClure et al., 1989; Takahashi et al., 1990). In future, the use of specific *cis*-acting promoter elements from auxin-responsive genes will provide an interesting functional test system to aid in the identification of auxin signalling elements and corresponding *trans*-acting factors which transduce the primary signal to the nucleus. Such rapid cellular responses to auxin application have prompted the search for putative auxin receptors, which after binding of this ligand may eventually lead, for example, to an up- or down-regulation of transcription and microtubule reorientation.

The relevance of auxin binding sites

In all these rapid responses to auxin application, the first step of the response must be an interaction of auxin with a receptor molecule, and in this regard auxin-binding proteins acquire particular significance. In the past two decades, sensitive ligand-binding techniques including photo-affinity labelling techniques have proven successful in the purification and molecular characterization of many hormone and drug receptors from a variety of organisms. This led to the identification of the first G-coupled receptors, now believed to be a ubiquitous family of proteins involved in sensing of a great variety of signals. This success is attributable in part to the development of new biochemical technologies and in part to the close functional coupling of these receptors to well-defined functional responses, e.g., the coupling to GTP-binding regulatory proteins (Dohlman et al., 1987). The lack of a suitable functional assay for a putative auxin receptor may explain why it is that although work towards its identification began at approximately the time characterization of G-coupled receptors was started, only now are we beginning to discover at the molecular level the functions of the proteins which have been found to bind auxin. Initially the search for auxin receptors was based on analysis of high-specificity binding of radiolabelled auxins to plant membrane fractions (Hertel et al., 1972). This approach led to the identification of three different types of auxin-binding site. In membranes from maize, auxin-binding sites were located at the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) (site I), the tonoplast (site II), and the plasma-membrane (site III), and found to have different binding affinities for different auxins (Dohrmann et al., 1978). For instance, site I and II have a high affinity for

1-NAA, whereas site III displayed a low affinity for 1-NAA and a higher affinity for IAA, 2,4-D, and 2-NAA (Hertel et al., 1983).

These sites were defined in purely operational terms by auxin-binding activities and, for most, any functional correlation with known auxin responses is still lacking. Therefore major efforts have been directed over the years towards identification of the active proteins at these sites, as well as their corresponding genes. It is expected that biochemical and genetic analysis will allow functions to be assigned to these binding sites. Due to the problems associated with the use of auxin-binding assays it is not surprising that it proved extremely difficult to biochemically characterize these operationally defined binding proteins (for discussion of problems see Venis, 1986). Therefore photo-affinity techniques, with proven advantages over equilibrium ligand binding assays, were employed in identifying auxin-binding proteins. Indeed, 5-azido[7-³H]indole-3-acetic acid (azido-IAA) could be demonstrated in bioassays to be an active auxin and exhibit a polar transport rate equivalent to that of free IAA (Melhado et al., 1981; Jones et al., 1984; Hicks et al., 1989a). Nevertheless, high background polypeptide labelling prevented the successful application of this technique for several years. After optimization of reaction conditions it was finally possible to demonstrate specific changes in auxin-binding proteins in the diageotropic (dgt) mutant of tomato. This mutant carries a spontaneous recessive mutation at a single locus, expresses auxin insensitivity, diageotropic shoot growth, abnormal vascular tissue, altered leaf morphology, and blockage of lateral root branching (Zobel, 1972; 1973). This correlates with reduced responsiveness of elongation growth to applied auxin, suggesting a lesion in the primary perception of the phytohormone as with the defects proposed for the auxin-resistant mutants of *A. thaliana* (Jackson, 1979; Bradford and Yang, 1980; Kelly and Bradford, 1986; Fujino et al., 1988). The photoaffinity labelling with azido-IAA of 40 to 42 kDa proteins in plasma membranes from stems of wild-type tomato plant which were almost undetectable in stem tissue of the dgt mutant, raises the prospect that, for the first time, phenotypic growth alterations can be directly related to biochemical properties of auxin-binding proteins (Hicks et al., 1989b). Application of this technology to a variety of plant tissues including plasma membranes from zucchini (*Cucurbita pepo*) or maize (*Zea mays*) resulted in the identification of proteins ranging from 40 up to 60 kDa, depending on the tissue analysed. An example of the specificity of labelling of polypeptides with 5-azido[7-³H]indole-3-acetic acid is shown in Fig. 3. The 60 kDa protein identified in plasma membranes from maize coleoptiles apparently represents an integral membrane protein which might be involved in the primary perception of IAA (Feldwisch and Palme, un-

Fig. 3. Photoaffinity labelling of maize plasmamembrane proteins with 5-azido[7-³H]indole-3-acetic acid. Sizes of molecular mass markers are given in right lane (in kDa).

published). It can be expected that with the help of azido-IAA as well as other auxin-specific photoaffinity ligands it will soon be possible to identify the variety of auxin-binding proteins proposed on the basis of ligand-binding assays (Hertel, 1987). We can further expect that dissection of the various auxin-specific responses of cells will soon be possible, following the advent of current molecular techniques.

The molecular structure of auxin-binding proteins located at the lumen of the endoplasmic reticulum (site I class)

From the many auxin-binding sites identified, a membrane-associated binding site from maize has been the most thoroughly studied. In maize and barnyard grass but not in other plants it is the most abundant auxin-binding moiety, and can be released from cellular fractions highly enriched for endoplasmic reticulum (Hertel et al., 1972; Dohrmann et al., 1978). Arguments in favour of this site being a putative receptor were the

specificity of binding of various auxin analogues, changes in site I-binding activity correlated with physiological events (Walton and Ray, 1981), and its absence in several auxin-insensitive mutants (Narayanan et al., 1981; Poovaiah, 1982). Additionally, inhibition of growth of maize mesocotyls by high-irradiance red light and growth alterations in artichoke tubers and tobacco cell cultures correlated with alterations in the degree of site I-specific auxin binding (Trewavas, 1980; Walton and Ray, 1981; Vreugdenhill et al., 1981). This binding activity is absent in strawberry mutants that fail to develop normal fruits after pollination (Poovaiah, 1982). The relative abundance of this protein in maize tissue allowed the isolation of its gene which should in turn allow the molecular basis of its function to be elucidated. Site I-specific auxin-binding proteins were solubilized first from maize coleoptiles or primary leaves as early as 1977 (Venis, 1977; Cross and Briggs, 1978; 1979). Subsequently, their presence was demonstrated in a series of other mono- and dicotyledonous plants. Technical problems associated with low concentration, pH lability of ligand binding, and lack of well-defined affinity purification techniques hampered purification of this protein. Several reports have pointed to a protein with a molecular mass of either approximately 20, 40 or 80 kDa that are probably formed by aggregation of monomeric units (for review see Venis, 1985). Shimomura and co-workers (Shimomura et al., 1986) using naphthalene-1-acetic acid coupled aminohexyl-Sepharose, succeeded in purification of a 20 kDa protein which bound 1-NAA with a K_D of 5.5×10^{-7} M, similar to characteristics attributed to site I-containing microsomal fractions. Further technical refinements resulted in the purification and subsequent protein sequence analysis of three related auxin-binding proteins from maize coleoptiles (Palme et al., 1990b). The major protein (ABP 1) had an apparent molecular mass of 22 kDa and bound 1-naphthylacetic acid with a K_D of 2.4×10^{-7} M. Scatchard analysis revealed that the homogeneous protein bound 895 pmol 1-naphthylacetic acid per nmol protein at pH 5.5, indicating one binding site per protein for this hormone. Other auxins such as indole-3-acetic acid, but not biologically inactive auxin analogues were able to compete efficiently for active ligand binding and pK_D values determined were in agreement with those obtained for the site I-specific binding activities (Ray et al., 1977; Dohrmann et al., 1978; Palme et al., 1989; Hesse et al., 1989; Palme et al., 1990 a,b). Furthermore, recombinant auxin-binding protein expressed and isolated from *E. coli* could be demonstrated to actively bind 1-NAA as well as IAA, clearly pointing to a functionally active auxin-binding protein (Hesse and Palme, unpublished data).

The primary structure was deduced from several cDNAs isolated from maize (Hesse et al., 1989; Inohara et al., 1989; Tillmann et al., 1989). Meanwhile, ad-

ditional members of this family were isolated from maize as well as other organisms (Palme et al., unpublished data). All proteins identified contain an N-terminal hydrophobic signal sequence of varying length (38 to 41 amino acids) and charge pattern. This signal could be demonstrated by *in vitro* assays to be responsible for the uptake of these proteins into dog and maize microsomes (Campos and Palme, unpublished data). The biochemical experiments reported have clearly established that the major auxin-binding protein is a luminal component of the ER (Hesse et al., 1989; Palme et al., 1990). This observation is confirmed by the absence of hydrophobic sequences responsible for membrane insertion in all members of the auxin-binding family identified so far. Furthermore, the presence of a C-terminal tetrapeptide sequence, -Lys-Asp-Glu-Leu (-KDEL) previously reported for other proteins to be a retention signal for the endoplasmic reticulum represents further evidence for the retention of ABP 1 in the lumen of the ER. The signal K/HDEL is now well recognized in eucaryotic organisms to be responsible for retrieval of proteins from a post ER salvage compartment by the active participation of a receptor system (for review see Warren, 1987; Semenza et al., 1990; Warren, 1990), and has apparently similar signal functions in plants. For example, using a chimeric reporter gene with a N-terminal leader for ER uptake and a C-terminal -KDEL sequence, Iturriaga and co-workers were able to demonstrate active retention of the reporter gene in the lumen of the ER only in the presence of the -KDEL sequence (Iturriaga et al., 1989). The demonstration of luminal ER localization of members of site I-specific auxin-binding proteins together with high resolution *in situ* detection techniques (Palme et al., unpublished data) contrasts with earlier claims for a localization of the maize auxin-binding protein to the outer surface of the outer epidermal cells (Löbner and Klämbt, 1985a,b). This discrepancy, confirmed by Shimomura et al. (1986) and others (Venis, personal communication), most likely reflects impermeability of the cell wall to immunoglobulins. The maize *axr*¹-gene was used as a heterologous hybridisation probe to isolate cDNA- and genomic clones of the corresponding *A. thaliana* gene *axrA-1* (Hesse, Schwonke and Palme, unpublished data). The *axrA-1* gene is located on chromosome 4 of *A. thaliana*, within 1 map unit of the *hy-4* gene (M. Yanofsky, personal communication). It can be expected that molecular analysis of the *axrA-1* gene from *A. thaliana*, encoding a protein of 22 kDa will significantly contribute to our understanding of the molecular mechanisms of ABP action (Palme et al., 1990).

Summary and Perspective

The existence of plant hormone receptors is proposed on the basis of experimental evidence and models devel-

oped for understanding perception and transduction of signals in a wide array of organisms ranging from bacteria to eucaryotes. In all systems studied perception of environmental stimuli was mostly linked to transmembrane sensor proteins, transmitting the signal proper to an intracellular regulator, which ultimately connects the signal with a physiological response. This general theme has been modulated and refined during evolution of eucaryotes from yeast to man, where organisms have efficiently adapted 'receiver' and 'transmitter' elements to sense an enormous variety of relevant signals.

The plant hormone auxin influences a diverse array of growth and differentiation processes including cell enlargement, cell division and vascular tissue differentiation. With the advent of molecular techniques it is now possible to study the molecular mechanisms regulated by this hormone. The elucidation of pathways along which the auxin signal is transmitted from the membrane to the nucleus will require the identification of receptors, the characterization of signal amplification elements that produce specific second messengers, and the analysis of nuclear components responsible for the various growth responses. It is expected that this type of analysis will eventually resolve the current theoretical controversy regarding the mechanism of phytohormone action and the relative importance of cellular sensitivity over phytohormone concentration. Evidently, the number and specificity of phytohormone receptors and the response pathways to which they are coupled in any particular cell or tissue will have a considerable influence on its primary responsive potential. The concentration of phytohormones either alone or in combination may simply affect the degree to which various aspects of this potential are realised; local changes in phytohormone concentration may be the way in which environmental signals are translated into appropriate plastic developmental responses. In this view, the basic body plan and the phytohormone responsiveness of individual cells would be determined by developmental programmes that are independent of phytohormones. Alternatively, it may be that different cells have essentially similar receptors and similar responsive potential, with different developmental fates and responses being determined largely by a complex series of phytohormone gradients. Environmental perturbation of these gradients could lead to the plastic developmental responses of higher plants. Trewavas (1986) has proposed an intriguing third alternative drawing on systems theory. As a consequence of an alteration in the environment, the metabolic system of a cell is proposed to alter in such a way that it now becomes sensitive to the effects of a particular phytohormone, resulting in the stimulation of certain developmental processes to the detriment of others. For example auxin-related stem cell elongation is stimulated as a consequence of the meta-

bolic alterations induced by low-light conditions. According to this model, plastic developmental responses are controlled by phytohormones in a manner that is relatively independent of both their concentration and the number of their receptors on a cell. At present, the experimental techniques are not available to address the relevance of any of these models to phytohormone action in vivo. This must await the development of techniques and biological probes to determine the phytohormone sensitivity of individual cells, the variety of response pathways in individual cells, the precise phytohormone concentrations experienced by individual cells, and the way these parameters are modified during development and in response to the environment. Once such techniques are available, the mechanisms and parameters that generate each of the known phytohormonal effects can gradually be deduced. This review describes the current attempts to elucidate the role that cellular sensitivity and phytohormone perception play in plant development.

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